

Piperidones as Potential Anticancer Agents

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Syntheses of some new 2,3,6-trisubstituted-4-piperidones have been described by condensation of aromatic aldehydes with ammonia or primary aliphatic amine and ketones under different reaction conditions.

A SERIES of azo compounds with nitrogen mustard moiety were synthesised¹ and screened for their antileukaemic activity. Several compounds of this nature were found active against Walker rat carcinoma 256. A study of structure-activity relationship of Schiff's bases without alkylating nitrogen mustard, revealed that azo-methine linkage is an essential structural unit for anti-tumour activity². Promising results³ have been also achieved from some piperidine derivatives in which 1-thio-phenoxy-2-chloro-3-(2-aminopiperidino) propanol was markedly effective against Sarcoma-180 and Ehrlich ascites Carcinoma.

These observations inspired us to synthesise 2,3,6-trisubstituted 4-piperidones of the type (I) and (II) which possess most of the structural requirements essential for significant activity. Piperidones of the type (I) were prepared⁴ by condensing aliphatic ketones with *p*-phenylazosalicylaldehyde⁵ and ammonium acetate in glacial acetic acid, while of the type (II) by condensation of ethylaceto-acetate with aromatic aldehydes and isopropyl amine or *n*-butylamine.

Experimental

All the m.ps. are uncorrected.

2,6-Di(2'-hydroxy-4'-phenylazo) phenyl-3-methyl-4-piperidone :

A mixture of ethyl methyl ketone (0.1 mole), *p*-phenylazo salicylaldehyde (0.2 mole), ammonium acetate (0.1 mole) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was gently refluxed for three hours. The mixture was then poured into water and left overnight. The brown

precipitate thus obtained was filtered, dried and crystallised by dissolving in little ether and then reprecipitating with petroleum ether (60°-80°), m.p. 165°, yield 70%. Found : N, 14.1; C₃₀H₂₇N₃O₃ requires : N, 13.86%.

I.R. spectrum of the compound shows an intense band in the carbonyl region at 1680 cm⁻¹ which reveals the presence of >C=O group. A medium band at 3440 cm⁻¹ is attributed for -NH stretching vibrations coupled with -OH stretching frequency.

Other compounds in this series were prepared in the same way and crystallised with benzene-petroleum ether; their relevant data are recorded in Table I.

N-Isopropyl-2,6-di (o-hydroxyphenyl)-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidone :

A mixture of isopropylamine (0.1 mole) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.1 mole) in a conical flask was cooled to 0° and then salicylaldehyde (0.2 mole) was added dropwise with swirling, and then left in a refrigerator for 24 hrs. The reaction content was poured into water and then extracted with benzene which was

then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Dry hydrochloric acid gas was then passed in the benzene solution when a gummy mass was obtained. This was dissolved in minimum amount of toluene and then precipitated by addition of petroleum ether. A brown solid of piperidone hydrochloride was obtained, m.p. 31°, yield 50%. Found : N, 3.6; C₂₃H₂₅NClO₅ requires : N, 3.2%.

I.R. spectrum of the compound shows a strong band at 1700 cm⁻¹ which is attributed for >C=O

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TABLE 1

Ref : Structure I

Sl. No.	R	R'	Yield %	M.P. °C
1.	H	H	50	175
2.	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	55	215
3.	H	COCH ₃	40	190
4.	H	C(CH ₃) ₂ OH	42	185d
5.	COOC ₂ H ₅	COOC ₂ H ₅	60	165

TABLE 2

Ref : Structure II

Sl. No.	R	R'	Yield %	M.P. °C
1.	n-C ₄ H ₉	o-(OH)C ₆ H ₄	30	42
2.	n-C ₄ H ₉	p-(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	35	30
3.	CH(CH ₃) ₂	p-(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	32	19
4.	CH(CH ₃) ₂	C ₆ H ₅	30	15

N.B. Analysis of all the compounds in Table 1 and 2 were found to be correct.

group. The intensity of the band is enhanced due to vicinal presence of ethoxycarbonyl group.

Other compounds in this series were prepared similarly, the analyses and other physical data are recorded in Table 2.

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